

The Cultural Evolution of Human Goals

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Abstract

Humans pursue remarkably diverse goals that vary over time and across cultures. These goals are both drivers and products of cultural evolutionary dynamics, yet most theories of cultural evolution have focused on the influence of culture on *how* individuals reach their goals, rather than on *which* goals they pursue. We argue that understanding the cultural dynamics of goals requires grounding them in the cognitive mechanisms through which individuals generate, evaluate, and select them. To this end, we draw on research on intrinsic motivation and curiosity in cognitive science and artificial intelligence to introduce the concept of *cultural autotelic agents*: individuals whose goal generation, anticipation, and selection mechanisms are shaped by, and in turn shape, their cultural environment. This framework reveals the key but underappreciated role of intrinsic motivation in promoting the diversity of goals and behaviors in ways that help sustain the open-ended nature of human culture.

1 Introduction

Cultural evolution theory seeks to explain how cultural traits like behaviors, ideas or technologies vary, spread, and improve over time (Boyd and Richerson, 1985; Henrich, 2015; Mesoudi and Thornton, 2018). Most work has focused on how cultural traits are transmitted and selected, studying the mechanisms of cultural transmission (Lewis and Laland, 2012; Caldwell and Millen, 2009; Lucas et al., 2020) and the learning strategies guiding cultural selection (Kendal et al., 2018; Rendell et al., 2010; Thompson et al., 2022). Far less attention has been paid to the role that *goals* play in shaping these dynamics. As Singh (2022) recently argued, goals act as subjective selection pressures on cultural evolution: they determine which cultural traits individuals perceive as valuable and selectively transmit, and they direct exploration and innovation toward fulfilling desired outcomes. The goal of “getting a man on the moon,” for instance, is what drove collective innovation in the specific direction that resulted in the Apollo 11 mission. Under this view, goals are major latent causal factors in the cultural evolution process — shaping not only which cultural traits spread, but also which are explored and refined.

If goals are latent drivers of cultural change, then understanding their dynamics becomes essential to building a comprehensive account of human cultural evolution. Across history and cultures, human goals have followed rich and diverse trajectories that likely reflect a combination of ecological pressures, individual cognitive mechanisms, and cultural transmission. Some goals, like predicting the weather, can be directly

18 linked to ecological demands (Chou, 1979). Others appear to resist such explanations: the goal of perfecting
19 spinning tops has endured for millennia despite little practical use (Piacentini and Delli Castelli, 2023; Best,
20 1976), and people today pursue eccentric goals such as creating drawings on digital GPS maps through elab-
21 orated running routes (Cantor, 2019) or parking in each and every spot of their local supermarket (Guardian,
22 2021). Still other goals point to intricate interactions with cultural environments: the emergence of the goal
23 of building flying machines (Velazquez, 2016), or the disappearance of the goal of transmuting metals into
24 gold (Principe, 2011), were consequences of changes in culturally inherited knowledge and beliefs. These
25 examples suggest that goals are not only drivers of cultural evolution, but also, at least in part, products of
26 it (Charbonneau et al., 2023). Goals and culture are thus linked by a feedback loop: cultural environments
27 shape which goals individuals pursue, and these goals in turn shape the cultural environment of other indi-
28 viduals and future generations. As Winters and Charbonneau (2026) argued in a recent commentary, these
29 reciprocal interactions are key to explaining the diversity of the goals humans pursue. Understanding this
30 feedback loop requires a dedicated account of how goals emerge, persist, and change under both ecological
31 and cultural pressures.

32 While Singh’s account acknowledges that cultural traits and beliefs can affect which goals are pursued, it
33 does not develop a full account of the feedback loop between goals and culture, nor identify the cognitive
34 processes involved (Singh, 2022). Two recent studies take a step further by modeling the co-evolution of goal
35 and solution spaces, which they argue may enable open-ended cultural evolution (Winters, 2019; Winters
36 and Charbonneau, 2025). These studies are macro-level: they represent goals as abstract targets in a solution
37 space, and vary the parameters determining the reciprocal influence between goals and solutions. While
38 very useful for exhaustively exploring the evolutionary regimes induced by different forms of goal-solution
39 coupling, these models do not aim to specify how goal dynamics actually operate in human populations —
40 that is, which cognitive mechanisms drive goal adoption, and how these mechanisms interact with cultural
41 environments. Without this grounding, it remains difficult to explain why human goal dynamics take the
42 specific forms they do, or to design experiments that could test these ideas empirically.

43 To address this gap, we draw on converging research in cognitive science and artificial intelligence that char-
44 acterizes humans as *autotelic agents* (from the Greek *auto* (self) and *telos* (goals)): individuals who actively
45 generate, anticipate, and select their own goals through cognitive and motivational mechanisms (Colas et al.,
46 2022b; Sigaud et al., 2022; Molinaro and Collins, 2023; Chu et al., 2024). This perspective shifts goals

47 from exogenous inputs to endogenous products of cognition, a move that has proven key to explaining and
48 modeling autonomous open-ended learning at the individual level (Sigaud et al., 2023). By embedding this
49 autotelic perspective within cultural evolution, we propose the framework of *cultural autotelic agents* (Fig-
50 ure 1): individuals whose goal-generation, anticipation and selection mechanisms are shaped by, and in turn
51 shape, their cultural environment (Section 2). This cognitive grounding reveals intrinsic motivation—the
52 drive to pursue activities for their inherent satisfaction rather than for instrumental value—as an under-
53 appreciated force in cultural evolution, one that may help explain why human cultures sustain continuous
54 innovation and diversification (Section 3). Finally, we discuss how combining experimental paradigms from
55 cognitive science and cultural evolution can enable the empirical study of goal dynamics (Section 4).

56 2 Cultural Autotelic Agents

57 This section introduces the cultural autotelic agent framework. We first define goals (Section 2.1), then
58 review the converging shift toward autotelic models of human behavior in cognitive science and artificial in-
59 telligence (Section 2.2), before describing how cultural environments interact with the cognitive mechanisms
60 underlying goal generation, anticipation, and selection (Section 2.3).

61 2.1 Defining goals

62 Definitions of goals vary across psychology, cognitive science, and artificial intelligence (Elliot and Fryer,
63 2008; Rolf and Asada, 2015; Colas et al., 2022b; Molinaro and Collins, 2023). Broadly, they converge on
64 the idea that a goal is a representation of a yet unrealized future that an individual is motivated to achieve.
65 Rather than committing to a single formalization, we focus on specifying the cognitive mechanisms that
66 lead to goal adoption, which are compatible with most formal definitions of goals. First, individuals must
67 be able to *generate* goals: to form mental representations of yet unrealized futures, whether specific target
68 states (e.g., going to the supermarket), sets of constraints on future world states (e.g., building a canoe to
69 carry 10 people across the river by the end of the week), desired mental states (e.g., learning about 14th
70 century Japanese history), or abstract objectives (e.g., building a thriving community). Second, they must
71 be able to *anticipate* the consequences of pursuing a goal: to mentally simulate what goal-directed behavior
72 would involve and lead to. And third, they must *select* among candidate goals: assess whether the anticipated

Figure 1: **Humans are cultural autotelic agents.** Understanding the feedback loop between goals and culture requires a model of how individuals generate, anticipate, and select goals within cultural environments. To this end, we propose to model humans as *cultural autotelic agents*. We situate this model along two dimensions: the origin of goals (exogenous vs. endogenous) and the mode of learning (individual vs. social). The left column reflects the prevalent assumption of exogenous goals. Under individual learning (top-left), this corresponds to the classical problem-solver model, where agents optimize behaviors toward externally-imposed objectives. Most experimental paradigms in cultural evolution extend this model by incorporating social learning, but retain the assumption that goals are externally imposed (bottom-left, e.g., transmission chains). Research on motivation, developmental psychology, and artificial intelligence has shifted the goal axis from exogenous to endogenous, introducing the concept of *autotelic agents*: individual learners able to generate, select, and pursue their own goals (top-right). We complete this picture by combining endogenous goals with social learning to propose the *cultural autotelic agent* (bottom-right): an individual whose goal-generation, anticipation, and selection mechanisms are shaped by, and in turn shape, their cultural environment.

73 outcomes align with their motivations, and commit to pursuing one over alternatives. Once selected, the goal
 74 representation drives goal-directed behavior, influencing cognitive processes such as attention, planning, and
 75 learning (Molinaro and Collins, 2023). Our analysis focuses on how cultural environments shape the three
 76 capacities of generation, anticipation, and selection, which structure our discussion in Section 2.3.

77 This framing distinguishes goals from related concepts such as rewards, incentives, and motivation (Rigoli,
 78 2026; Dayan and Balleine, 2002; Silver et al., 2021; Rigoli and Lennon, 2025). In the decision-making
 79 literature, a reward function refers to a real-valued function on the space of possible outcomes: it ascribes

80 positive value (rewards) to desirable outcomes, and negatives values (punishments) to undesirable outcomes,
81 with rewards and punishments sometimes collectively referred to as incentives (Rigoli, 2026). Under this
82 definition, those concepts are related to the mechanisms underlying goal selection: by characterizing the
83 motivations of an individual, they help predict whether an individual will select a given goal based on the
84 anticipated outcomes. As such, goals and incentives are distinct concepts: an individual may be motivated to
85 win a marathon (the goal) because they expect to obtain social recognition (the incentive). Therefore, asking
86 how cultural environments shape goal adoption is different from exploring how they shape reward function:
87 in addition to considering cultural influences on motivation (i.e. goal selection mechanisms), it requires to
88 investigate how social information affects goal generation and goal anticipation mechanisms. Finally, the
89 broad framing we adopt is agnostic to hierarchical structure: whether a goal is pursued as an end in itself or
90 as a step toward another goal, what matters is that the individual generates it, anticipates its consequences,
91 and is motivated to select and pursue it.

92 **2.2 A converging shift toward autotelic agents**

93 Most work in psychology and artificial intelligence treats goals as exogenous starting points: experimenters
94 define the goal, align participants' motivation accordingly, and study how behaviors are optimized to reach
95 it (Karayanni and Nelken, 2022; Molinaro and Collins, 2023; Sutton et al., 1998; Liu et al., 2022, Figure 1,
96 top-left). The same applies to cultural evolution experiments, most saliently in transmission chain designs,
97 where participants might be asked to maximize the flying distance of paper airplanes (Caldwell and Millen,
98 2008) or the rolling speed of a wheel (Derex et al., 2019), with the experimenter defining the goal and aligning
99 participants' motivation accordingly (Mesoudi, 2021, Figure 1, bottom-left). This approach has facilitated the
100 study of problem-solving, but has left the origins of goals unexplained. Inspired by early research on intrinsic
101 motivation and self-determination (Berlyne, 1960; Deci, 1972), as well as theories of active learning (Piaget
102 and Cook, 1952; Gopnik et al., 1999), recent work in cognitive science has begun to explore the mechanisms
103 underlying autonomous goal generation and selection (Ten et al., 2021; Poli et al., 2022; Chu and Schulz,
104 2022; Chu, 2023; Molinaro et al., 2024). Developments in artificial intelligence mirror this shift: where
105 traditional reinforcement learning agents maximize externally defined reward functions (Sutton et al., 1998;
106 Liu et al., 2022), autotelic agents internally generate and select goals to pursue based on intrinsic learning
107 signals (Srivastava et al., 2013; Baranes and Oudeyer, 2013; Santucci et al., 2016; Forestier et al., 2017;

108 Colas et al., 2022b, Figure 1, top-right). Together, these parallel developments provide the foundation for a
109 cognitive account of goal evolution: one grounded in the mechanisms through which individuals generate,
110 anticipate, and select their own goals.

111 Combining autotelic learning with social information is a natural next step that several recent studies have
112 begun to take. The framework of *teachable autotelic agents* considers agents who generate their own goals
113 but can also learn goal representations from social feedback, demonstrations, or instructions (Colas et al.,
114 2020; Akakzia et al., 2020; Sigaud et al., 2022). More recent work leverages large language models as cultural
115 mediators, allowing agents to generate goals shaped by shared linguistic representations and norms (Colas
116 et al., 2023; Du et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2023). These contributions show that social information not only
117 accelerates skill acquisition but can also expand the space of conceivable goals (Colas et al., 2022a), paving
118 the way for an integrated framework bridging autotelic learning and cultural evolution. In the next section,
119 we develop this integration by examining how cultural environments interact with the cognitive mechanisms
120 underlying goal generation, anticipation, and selection.

121 **2.3 A cognitive foundation for goal evolution**

122 By connecting perspectives from autotelic learning and cultural evolution, our proposed framework of *cul-*
123 *tural autotelic agents* (Figure 1, bottom-right) lets us describe how culture influences goal pursuit through
124 three interacting mechanisms: goal generation, anticipation, and selection. In turn, the goal-directed behav-
125 iors of individuals reshape the cultural environment of their contemporaries and future generations, embed-
126 ding goals in a culturally-mediated feedback loop (Figure 2).

127 **Goal generation.** Before pursuing a goal, an individual must first think of it. This requires both being
128 able to represent the goal and being likely to generate it among the many possible goals one could represent.
129 Which goals can be represented, and which are likely to be generated, depends on the individual’s experience
130 and social context. We discuss several ways in which cultural environments shape this process.

131 Some goals are directly transmitted through teaching and explicit instruction, whereby individuals actively
132 help learners acquire a similar goal representation as their own. When goals are not explicitly stated, ob-
133 servers can reconstruct the original goals of others from their behavioral cues through goal inference (Wood-

Figure 2: **The feedback loop between goals and cultural environments is grounded in individual cognition.** Individuals generate, anticipate, and select goals through cognitive mechanisms that are influenced by their cultural environment. Goal generation is shaped by exposure to others’ goals — through teaching, goal inference, or simple observation — which determines both which goals an individual can represent and which are likely to come to mind. Goal anticipation depends on an internal world model — a set of expectations about how the world works, what actions are possible, and what outcomes they produce — used to simulate the likely outcomes of goal pursuit. This world model is shaped by culturally inherited beliefs and vicarious learning, as well as by cultural niche construction, which alters the world dynamics themselves. Goal selection depends on the individual’s motivations, which are influenced by cultural mechanisms such as conformity, goal contagion, and imitative incentive learning. In return, the goal-directed behaviors of individuals reshape the cultural environment encountered by contemporaries and future generations, closing a feedback loop between goals and culture.

134 ward, 1998; Gergely and Csibra, 2003). Computational accounts suggest this relies on inverse decision-
 135 making: observers invert a model of goal-directed behavior to infer the preferences or reward structures that
 136 best explain the observed actions (Jara-Ettinger et al., 2016; Jern et al., 2017; Collette et al., 2017; Charp-
 137 entier et al., 2020). This exposure to others’ goals biases individuals’ goal generation processes: observed
 138 goals are more cognitively accessible than goals that must be imagined from scratch. Having witnessed
 139 someone skipping stones, for instance, makes this goal easier to think of. Studies of construct accessibility

140 further suggest that recency and frequency of exposure increase the likelihood of retrieval (Higgins et al.,
141 1982, 1985).

142 Beyond biasing the sampling of existing goals, cultural environments shape which novel goals individuals
143 can generate. The goals an individual has been exposed to determine the building blocks available for imag-
144 ining new ones. The notion of “structured imagination” captures this idea: knowledge of existing concepts
145 constrains what can be imagined, leading individuals to base new creations on familiar components (Ward,
146 1994). A recent study confirmed this empirically: participants prompted to invent new grid-based strategy
147 games were more likely to introduce atypical mechanics (i.e. not found in Tic-Tac-Toe) when those mechan-
148 ics already existed in the examples they had been exposed to (Collins et al., 2025).

149 These cognitive processes have computational analogues that offer avenues for formal modeling. In artificial
150 intelligence, goal-space learning algorithms rely on generative models to produce goals, training them on
151 previously encountered goals and observations (Péré et al., 2018; Nair et al., 2018; Laversanne-Finot et al.,
152 2021). Other algorithms explicitly capture compositional goal generation, where agents construct new goals
153 by recombining elements from socially observed ones (Colas et al., 2020). More broadly, the emerging
154 framework of goals as compositional programs formalizes this intuition: which new goals can be synthe-
155 sized depends on the library of primitives available, which is itself a product of the individual’s cultural
156 environment (Davidson et al., 2025b).

157 **Goal anticipation.** Once a goal has been generated, an individual must anticipate what pursuing it would
158 involve and lead to. This requires simulating the consequences of goal-directed behavior using an internal
159 world model: a set of expectations about how the world works, what one is capable of, and what outcomes
160 one’s actions produce. Cultural environments shape this anticipation process in two ways: by shaping world
161 models themselves, and by shaping the world dynamics they represent.

162 First, culture shapes world models through social information. On one hand, it shapes expectations about
163 the external world. Observing the outcomes of others’ actions updates one’s beliefs about the environment:
164 seeing an individual dig the ground to collect wild yam can teach another that such tubers can be found
165 in the ground, a fact they may not have discovered on their own. Stories, fiction, and culturally inherited
166 beliefs extend this beyond direct observation—beliefs about witchcraft, for instance, lead individuals to

167 anticipate that failing to pursue spiritual protection will have adverse consequences (Singh, 2022). On the
168 other hand, culture shapes expectations about oneself (Bandura et al., 1986; Jin et al., 2023). Observing others
169 with similar backgrounds succeed or struggle at particular tasks can calibrate expectations about one's own
170 learning trajectory, affecting which goals are anticipated to be achievable or rewarding to pursue. Here too,
171 cultural narratives play a role, shaping beliefs about what members of one's group can accomplish (Steele
172 and Aronson, 1995). This social learning aligns world models across generations, leading individuals with
173 similar knowledge and cultural backgrounds to anticipate similar outcomes for similar goals.

174 Second, culture shapes the world dynamics themselves. Cultural activities transform the physical and social
175 environment through niche construction, changing how we pursue goals and how likely we are to achieve
176 them. The anticipated consequences of pursuing the goal of "crossing the river," for instance, depend on
177 whether previous generations have built a bridge. The cultural transmission of cognitive tools and skills fur-
178 ther transforms how individuals pursue goals and what they can achieve (Heyes, 2018): "memorizing large
179 amounts of information" becomes a different undertaking once mnemonic techniques such as the "memory
180 palace" are available (Chrisomalis and Miton, 2026; Riggsby, 2026). Finally, cultural environments can also
181 shape downstream consequences of a goal's achievement: "predicting the weather" leads to very different
182 downstream outcomes in a farming community than in a foraging community. By shaping both the world
183 models individuals use to simulate outcomes and the world dynamics these models represent, cultural en-
184 vironments reshape the consequences that individuals anticipate when evaluating candidate goals, and thus
185 which goals appear worth pursuing.

186 **Goal selection** While social information shapes which goals can be represented and how their conse-
187 quences are anticipated, goal selection ultimately depends on whether the anticipated outcome aligns with
188 the individual's motivations. Highlighting motivation as a key cognitive mechanism for understanding goal
189 dynamics is one of the main contributions of embedding autotelic learning within cultural evolution. Mo-
190 tivation is typically classified by psychologists into two main types: intrinsic and extrinsic (Ryan and Deci,
191 2000). Extrinsic motivation refers to an individual's desire to pursue a goal because of the external reward
192 (e.g., food, money, or social praise) associated with its completion. Intrinsic motivations, by contrast, are
193 characterized by doing an activity "for its inherent satisfaction rather than for some separable consequence"
194 (Ryan and Deci, 2000, p. 56). A classic example of intrinsically motivating activities is that of solving puzzles

195 (Chu et al., 2024). Several theories have been proposed to characterize what makes an activity intrinsically
196 motivating (Oudeyer and Kaplan, 2007; Ten et al., 2022; Blain and Sharot, 2021), including optimal in-
197 congruity (Dember and Earl, 1957; Hunt, 1965), intermediate novelty (Berlyne, 1960), optimal challenge
198 (Cziksentmihalyi, 1990; Kidd and Hayden, 2015), and learning progress (Ten et al., 2021; Poli et al., 2022,
199 2025; Molinaro et al., 2024).

200 Both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation play a role in the cultural selection of goals. The multi-generational
201 persistence of the goal of accurately predicting weather, for instance, is clearly linked to its extrinsic instru-
202 mental value. In other cases, a goal’s tie to intrinsic motivation may help explain its cultural success: Brecher
203 et al. (2014) suggests that “one of the things that makes a [spinning] top so engaging is its counter-intuitive
204 behavior.” Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation thus jointly determine which goals make it into the next gener-
205 ation’s cultural environment, shaping downstream goal representation and anticipation as discussed above.

206 Cultural transmission can also reshape motivations more directly. Goal contagion occurs when observing
207 someone pursue a goal enhances the observer’s own motivation to pursue it (Aarts et al., 2004). Empiri-
208 cal evidence suggests that this only occurs for goals the individual already values, making goal contagion
209 a mechanism that amplifies and spreads existing motivations within a population rather than creating new
210 ones. Beyond goal contagion, a growing body of computational and neuroimaging work demonstrates that
211 social observation can durably reshape an individual’s own value representations. Observing another per-
212 son’s moral preferences can shift one’s own fairness values through reinforcement learning (FeldmanHall
213 et al., 2018), and learning another’s preferences induces neural plasticity that brings one’s own value rep-
214 resentations closer to theirs (Garvert et al., 2015; Najar et al., 2020). While these mechanisms reshape or
215 amplify existing motivations, imitative incentive learning can expand the motivational landscape entirely:
216 observing another individual pursue an outcome can lead the observer to treat that outcome as valuable in it-
217 self (Rigoli, 2026). A study by Greer and Singer-Dudek (2008) indeed suggested that children who observed
218 a peer receive an arbitrary object while completing a task became motivated to acquire this same object, even
219 though it had no motivational value before observing the peer receive it. Because the object was never paired
220 with any pre-existing reward, it appears to have become valued as an end in itself rather than as a means to
221 other incentives. Imitative incentive learning thus provides a pathway through which cultural transmission
222 creates genuinely new motivations across generations (see also Rigoli and Lennon, 2025, for a framework
223 connecting these mechanisms to cultural evolution of values).

224 **Closing the loop: how goals reshape the cultural environment.** The three mechanisms above describe
225 how cultural environments shape which goals individuals generate, anticipate, and select. But the goals indi-
226 viduals pursue also reshape the cultural environment, closing the feedback loop. For instance, a community
227 that pursues athletic achievement builds stadiums and training facilities that make new physical goals con-
228 ceivable (generation), produces visible exemplars whose successes and failures shape others' expectations
229 about what athletic goals are achievable (anticipation), and creates social prestige systems that make athletic
230 pursuits more motivating (selection). Importantly, not all domains generate equally strong feedback through
231 these mechanisms. Pursuing scientific or technological goals reshapes both world models and ecological
232 niches in ways that transform how future goals in the same domain are anticipated, creating self-reinforcing
233 dynamics. In contrast, goals such as skipping stones reshape the cultural environment only minimally. This
234 asymmetry may help explain why some cultural domains display open-ended evolutionary dynamics while
235 others remain relatively stable — a question we turn to in the next section.

236 **3 Intrinsic Motivation and Open-Ended Cultural Evolution**

237 The framework above identifies the three mechanisms of generation, anticipation, and selection through
238 which cultural environments shape the goals individuals pursue, and through which those goals in turn shape
239 the cultural environment. But this feedback loop does not, on its own, guarantee open-ended cultural change.
240 It could just as well converge toward a fixed repertoire of goals and solutions. Yet human cultures are remark-
241 ably open-ended, fostering continuous diversification and improvement (Stanley, 2019; Derex, 2022; Winters
242 and Charbonneau, 2025; Morgan and Feldman, 2024). What sustains this open-endedness?

243 Exaptation and recombination have been identified as crucial mechanisms for open-ended cultural evolution
244 (Enquist et al., 2011; Andriani and Cattani, 2016; Winters, 2019; Derex and Mesoudi, 2020). Exaptation
245 occurs when a trait developed for one purpose is co-opted for another; recombination occurs when exist-
246 ing cultural elements are combined into new solutions. Both produce innovations that could not have been
247 reached through gradual optimisation for one specific function. — e.g., incrementally improving conven-
248 tional ovens, no matter how long, would never have led to the microwave oven. Both mechanisms require
249 some degree of serendipity: exaptation relies on unintended functionalities in existing traits, and recom-
250 bination relies on unanticipated synergies between independently discovered traits. We argue that intrinsic

251 motivation reduces this dependence on chance in three ways: by preserving promising innovations until their
252 potential can be realized, by driving open-ended goal dynamics that continuously expand the space of ex-
253 plored goals, and by maintaining inter-individual diversity that broadens the collective repertoire from which
254 new combinations can emerge.

255 **Intrinsic motivation preserves promising innovations** Exaptation and recombination can occur by re-
256 purposing an innovation that already had instrumental value. For instance, early computers were built using
257 vacuum tubes, which were previously used to detect radio waves (Stanley and Lehman, 2015), and microwave
258 ovens were invented by co-opting a technology initially used for radar magnetron (Andriani and Cattani,
259 2016). However, many innovations emerge long before any instrumental application is recognized. Ad-
260 vances in number theory preceded their use in cryptography (Wagner, 2023); ancient Greeks studied static
261 electricity centuries before it was harnessed for any practical purpose (Beck, 1986; Derex, 2022); and the
262 discovery of the wheel predated its use for cattle-drawn transport (Ekholm, 1946; Matuschik, 2006; Riede
263 et al., 2021). Mathematical models of cultural adaptation have highlighted the importance of this adaptive
264 standing variation — the existence of cultural traits whose instrumental value will only be realized after an en-
265 vironmental change (Fogarty and Kandler, 2020). These models indicate that standing variation is especially
266 likely to support cultural adaptation in the presence of foresight mechanisms, which introduce and preserve
267 variants that will be useful in the future. While short-term foresight may be supported by cognitive mech-
268 anisms such as mental time-travel (Suddendorf and Corballis, 2007; Mesoudi, 2008), it cannot explain why
269 some innovations remain dormant for centuries, as is the case in the examples above. The autotelic cultural
270 perspective we introduced provides key insights into this question. Indeed, theories of intrinsic motivation
271 predict that individuals are drawn to goals that produce surprising yet learnable effects: outcomes where new
272 information can be gained and where downstream consequences can eventually be predicted and controlled
273 (Schmidhuber, 1991; Kaplan and Oudeyer, 2004; Ten et al., 2021). Goals with such properties, controllable
274 processes with rich causal structure, are precisely those most likely to serve as building blocks for future
275 innovations. Under this view, promising innovations are not introduced because of their anticipated value,
276 but because they are the outcome of goals that are intrinsically motivating. The mechanisms supporting the
277 feedback loop described in the previous section are key to understanding why these non-instrumental goals
278 are repeatedly pursued across generations, a central requirement for preserving knowledge until it can be
279 exapted for instrumental purposes.

280 This argument connects to a body of literature on the role of play in cultural evolution (Miu et al., 2026;
281 Riede et al., 2018; Meyer and Riede, 2025; Riede et al., 2021, 2022; Boyette, 2024; Lew-Levy et al., 2020),
282 which describes play as promoting innovation by familiarizing individuals with the affordances of their en-
283 vironment. The autotelic perspective complements this view by shifting focus from play as preparation for
284 instrumental innovation to play as a context of non-instrumental discovery (Chu, 2023; Chu et al., 2024). In
285 this literature, correlations between the abundance of non-utilitarian objects (e.g. toys, miniatures) and pe-
286 riods of cultural innovation (Meyer and Riede, 2025; Riede et al., 2021) have been interpreted as suggestive
287 evidence that play unlocks later innovative capacities. We additionally hypothesize that they reflect cultural
288 environments promoting greater reliance on intrinsic motivation in goal selection, leading to discoveries
289 preserved as toys or miniatures before their instrumental value is recognized.

290 **Intrinsic motivation drives open-ended goal dynamics.** Intrinsic motivation may also be key to explain-
291 ing how the feedback loop between goals and cultural environments produces open-ended dynamics. Indeed,
292 existing models suggest that open-ended trajectories require the existence of perturbations that maintain the
293 co-evolution between goals and solutions out of equilibrium (Winters and Charbonneau, 2025). By being
294 largely state-dependent, intrinsic motivation may produce such perturbations: what counts as novel, sur-
295 prising, or optimally challenging shifts as cultural groups learn new skills. In contrast to the stochastic
296 perturbations modeled in Winters and Charbonneau (2025), intrinsic motivation gives directionality to these
297 open-ended trajectories — goals do not merely drift but tend toward increasing complexity and qualitative
298 novelty. In artificial intelligence, this dynamic is captured by automatic curriculum learning methods: agents
299 that select training goals based on intrinsic motivation naturally progress from simple to complex tasks, each
300 mastered goal serving as a stepping stone to the next (Portelas et al., 2020). By contrast, agents that pur-
301 sue externally specified objectives often get stuck in local optima, unable to discover solutions that require
302 indirect paths (Lehman and Stanley, 2011). Exporting those insights to cultural evolution may help explain
303 cultural transitions that extrinsic motivation alone cannot account for. Early bow prototypes, for instance,
304 were likely less efficient than existing spear-throwers and would have been abandoned if instrumental value
305 was the only criterion. Purely extrinsic incentives would thus be unlikely to steer inter-generational refine-
306 ments towards fully functioning bows. In contrast, curiosity about flexible materials may have motivated the
307 sustained pursuit of increasingly complex goals, ultimately allowing bows to surpass existing technologies
308 (Derech, 2022). As such, intrinsic motivation not only introduces and preserves adaptive standing variation,

309 as discussed in the previous paragraph: it also implements feedback dynamics that build on that standing
310 variation to discover innovations that are increasingly likely to be exapted for instrumental purposes.

311 **Intrinsic motivation maintains inter-individual diversity.** While the previous two mechanisms operate
312 at the individual level, intrinsic motivation also promotes exaptation and recombination at the collective
313 level by maintaining diversity in the goals explored within a population. Extrinsically motivating goals can
314 vary between individuals because of factors such as differences in access to resources or specializations, but
315 intrinsic motivation introduces additional sources of path-dependence that further promote goal diversity.
316 What is surprising, learnable, or novel for a given individual depends on their particular history of skill
317 and knowledge acquisition. A child playing with blocks might be motivated to build the tallest possible
318 tower because they have recently experienced progress toward this goal, while another child with the same
319 blocks might prefer to build a house. Intrinsic motivation thus generates divergent exploration trajectories,
320 producing substantial goal diversity at the group level. This diversity matters because it is a key enabler of
321 exaptation and recombination (Schimmelfennig et al., 2021; Smaldino et al., 2024): a group whose members
322 explore different goals accumulates a broader repertoire of skills and knowledge, increasing the probability
323 that some will later prove useful in combination or for unforeseen purposes. Previous work has shown that
324 specific social network structures can help sustain such diversity (Nisioti et al., 2022; Derex and Boyd, 2016;
325 Cantor et al., 2021). Intrinsic motivation offers a complementary source of diversification: one that operates
326 at the level of individual goal selection.

327 **4 Developing methods for studying culturally evolving goals**

328 The framework developed above makes specific claims about how cultural environments shape goal gen-
329 eration, anticipation, and selection, and about how intrinsic motivation contributes to open-ended cultural
330 dynamics. Testing these claims requires empirical approaches that allow goals to vary and evolve, yet current
331 methods in cultural evolution are not well suited to this: participants are almost always passive recipients of
332 goals defined by experimenters. A promising direction is to combine methodological tools from cognitive
333 science, where autotelic learning is increasingly studied, with experimental designs from cultural evolution,
334 where social transmission is well controlled. We first discuss how this combination could allow us to study

335 goal evolutionary dynamics in the lab, before turning to promising real-world datasets. We conclude with a
336 discussion of the analytical tools needed to represent goals and characterize their evolution.

337 **4.1 Goal evolution in the lab**

338 The three experimental paradigms below offer complementary entry points into studying goal dynamics: the
339 first targets goal selection, the second goal generation, and the third captures the full feedback loop between
340 goals and cultural transmission.

341 **The free-choice paradigm.** A well-established experimental design to study motivation is the free-choice
342 paradigm (Deci, 1971, 1972; Izuma and Murayama, 2013; Ten et al., 2021; Molinaro et al., 2024; Poli et al.,
343 2022), in which participants are provided with several learning activities among which they can freely choose.
344 Ten et al. (2021), for instance, used this paradigm to show that extrinsically motivated individuals spend more
345 time on unlearnable activities than intrinsically motivated ones, suggesting that intrinsic motivation leads to
346 more adaptive goal selection. Combining the free-choice paradigm with experimental designs from cul-
347 tural evolution would allow us to explore how social learning interacts with goal selection. A transmission
348 chain design would reveal how goal selection changes across cultural generations, while closed-group de-
349 signs, where participants exchange information within a group (Mesoudi, 2021), could test whether mixing
350 intrinsically and extrinsically motivated individuals affects the collective exploration of the goal space. This
351 latter design would be directly relevant to the claim made in Section 3 that intrinsic motivation maintains
352 inter-individual diversity in goals.

353 **Open-ended game design.** While the free-choice paradigm is well-suited to studying goal selection, partic-
354 ipants can only choose among goals defined by the experimenters. It does not address how new goals emerge.
355 Experimental paradigms involving open-ended game design target this question directly. This class of ex-
356 periments lets participants design playful goals in open-ended environments such as Minecraft (e.g. “Jump
357 from a mountain into a body of water”) (Todd et al., 2025), a physics-based throwing domain (e.g. “Throw
358 the ball so it hits the wall then bounces back to you”) (Davidson et al., 2025a), or the space of board games
359 (e.g. “4 in a row wins, but only diagonal.”) (Collins et al., 2025). These studies have revealed how partic-
360 ipants’ experience with the environment affects the kind of goals they invent (Todd et al., 2025), and how

361 exposure to examples shapes the generation of new games (Collins et al., 2025). Combining these paradigms
362 with cultural evolution designs would allow us to study how socially transmitted goals shape the generation
363 of new ones across individuals and generations.

364 **Picbreeder.** The paradigm closest to capturing the full feedback loop between autotelic learning and cul-
365 tural evolution is perhaps *Picbreeder* (Secretan et al., 2008). In this online experiment, users “bred” images
366 by applying simple commands whose effects were initially unknown. Users selected “parent” images to cre-
367 ate modified “offspring,” and could publish images they liked, making them available as starting points for
368 others. This amounted to a collective, open-ended exploration with no externally defined goal: there was no
369 criterion dictating which images should be selected. From initially amorphous images, this process eventu-
370 ally produced complex images resembling real objects such as butterflies, landscapes, and cars. Strikingly,
371 the authors found that trying to re-discover these images using an objective-driven algorithm often failed,
372 with optimization remaining stuck in local optima. This result directly illustrates the argument developed
373 in Section 3: intrinsically motivated collective exploration can reach outcomes that objective-driven search
374 cannot. Large-scale experiments in the spirit of Picbreeder hold great potential for studying the cultural
375 co-evolution of goals and solutions.

376 However, Picbreeder also highlights a key limitation: because the platform did not record users’ intentions,
377 we do not know what goals they actually pursued. Some users may have explored without any specific tar-
378 get, while others likely had concrete objectives in mind, such as producing an image resembling a particular
379 object. This ambiguity makes it difficult to study the goal dynamics themselves. Future experiments in this
380 spirit would benefit from combining open-ended collective exploration with methods for eliciting partic-
381 ipants’ goals, for instance by prompting users to describe their current objective at regular intervals, or by
382 allowing them to annotate their creations with intended targets. Such designs would make it possible to study
383 not only the evolution of cultural artifacts, but also the generation, selection, and transmission of the goals
384 that drive them.

385 4.2 Promising datasets

386 Beyond controlled experiments, studying real-world datasets such as patent citations has been informative for
387 cultural evolution research (Fleming, 2001). However, such analyses have typically focused on behavioral
388 outputs (e.g. how components are recombined) rather than on the goals that motivated them. Several digi-
389 tal platforms now offer promising opportunities to study goal dynamics more directly, because they contain
390 traces of how users define, refine, and share objectives over time. GitHub¹ records how software develop-
391 ers iteratively define and refine project objectives through issues and documentation. Its forking structure,
392 where users copy and modify entire projects, provides a natural analogue to cultural transmission of goals:
393 inherited objectives are adapted to new contexts, and the issue and pull-request system reveals how collec-
394 tive feedback reshapes goals over time. Notably, many open-source projects originate from intrinsic moti-
395 vation — developers “scratching a personal itch” (Raymond, 1999) — and only later acquire broader instru-
396 mental value, illustrating how non-instrumental pursuits can seed consequential innovations. Scratch² allows
397 users to “remix” others’ programs, providing a phylogenetic structure in which self-defined creative goals are
398 visibly inherited and modified. Remix trees could enable tracking of goal lineages across creators, including
399 cases where users repurpose existing programs for entirely different goals — a form of goal-level exaptation.
400 Perhaps most promising is the online game One Hour One Life,³ which simulates inter-generational cultural
401 accumulation: each player lives a single in-game life and inherits the cultural repertoire built by previous
402 players. Vélez et al. (2024) reports a player saying “*I spent my [character’s] life entirely dedicated to tak-*
403 *ing a picture. We [the online community] already had a camera, so a huge chunk of the work was already*
404 *done.*”⁴ This illustrates directly how accumulated cultural repertoires shape goal generation: the existence
405 of a camera made “taking a picture” a conceivable and motivating goal. As with Picbreeder, however, a
406 key challenge with these platforms is that goals must typically be inferred from behavioral traces rather than
407 observed directly, a difficulty we return to below.

¹<https://github.com>

²<https://scratch.mit.edu>

³<https://onehouronelife.net>

⁴reported in a talk at IPAM, UCLA: <https://www.ipam.ucla.edu/abstract/?tid=20600&pcode=MOIWS1>

408 **4.3 Analytical tools**

409 Analyzing the evolution of goals poses challenges beyond those faced when studying the evolution of behav-
410 iors. The first concerns how to record and represent goals. As noted above, goals are internal representations
411 that cannot be directly observed. In experimental settings, participants can be prompted to describe their
412 aims verbally, specify evaluation criteria, or provide demonstrations that can be translated into formal repre-
413 sentations through methods such as program synthesis (Davidson et al., 2025b,a). In existing datasets, goals
414 must be inferred from behavioral traces, an approach that introduces substantial uncertainty. Beyond the
415 question of recording, the choice of computational representation matters: options range from hand-coded
416 goal spaces (Mankowitz et al., 2018; Akakzia et al., 2020; Team et al., 2023) to neural network embeddings
417 (Hermann et al., 2017; Colas et al., 2020) and reward-producing programs (Davidson et al., 2025b), each
418 with different trade-offs in expressiveness, interpretability, and scalability.

419 A second challenge lies in characterizing the evolution of goal populations over time. Once goals can be
420 represented, researchers need metrics that capture their diversity, complexity, and relatedness within a pop-
421 ulation and track how these change across generations. Programmatic representations offer a promising
422 direction, as they make it possible to project goals onto structured spaces where similarity and novelty are
423 easier to quantify (Davidson et al., 2025b). Beyond static snapshots, understanding goal dynamics will re-
424 quire methods to track goal lineages and measure their transmission, recombination, and persistence over
425 time. Tools from phylogenetics and population genetics provide natural starting points: just as phylogenetic
426 methods reconstruct the branching history of biological species or cultural artifacts (Takezaki and Nei, 1996;
427 Tehrani and Collard, 2009; Tehrani and d’Huy, 2016), analogous approaches could be used to trace how
428 goals branch, merge, and go extinct across generations of learners.

429 **5 Conclusion**

430 We argued that goals are not merely inputs to cultural evolution but display rich cultural evolutionary dy-
431 namics, mediated by cultural influences on the cognitive mechanisms underlying goal pursuit. By modeling
432 individuals as cultural autotelic agents, we grounded these dynamics in the specific cognitive mechanisms
433 of goal generation, anticipation, and selection; each of which interacts with cultural environments in dis-

434 tinct ways. This framework reveals intrinsic motivation as an underappreciated force in cultural evolution,
435 one that biases exploration toward goals with rich causal structure, sustains non-instrumental pursuits long
436 enough for their potential to be realized, and maintains inter-individual diversity in the goals explored within
437 a population.

438 A question we have not addressed is whether goal evolutionary dynamics constitute a Darwinian process.
439 While we consider this question largely open, our framework provides a useful lens for approaching it. In
440 some cases, the cultural stability of a goal clearly depends on the transmission of the goal representation
441 itself: goals such as playing Solitaire or skipping stones are unlikely to be generated independently and
442 require direct exposure to be acquired. In other cases, inter-generational stability is maintained not through
443 transmission of the representation but through cultural shaping of the mechanisms that produce it: a child
444 who observes an adult climb a tree to collect honey does not necessarily inherit a new goal representation
445 but updates their world model, which in turn makes this goal more likely to be selected. Our framework
446 suggests that these are not two types of goals but two routes through which culture stabilizes goals — via
447 generation mechanisms in the first case, via anticipation and selection mechanisms in the second. Whether
448 these dynamics are best described as Darwinian, or whether the diversity of transmission routes and the role
449 of individual-level recombination call for a different evolutionary framework, remains an important open
450 question.

451 These open questions call for new empirical and computational approaches. On the empirical side, studying
452 goal dynamics requires experimental designs in which goals are free to vary rather than imposed by exper-
453 imenters. As outlined in Section 4, combining paradigms from autotelic learning (free-choice, open-ended
454 game design) with transmission designs from cultural evolution offers a concrete path forward. On the com-
455 putational side, building multi-agent simulations of cultural autotelic agents — where agents generate their
456 own goals, transmit them socially, and evolve them over generations — would allow testing the predictions
457 of our framework, for instance whether intrinsic motivation promotes open-ended cultural dynamics in sil-
458 ico. More broadly, we hope this work encourages dialogue between cultural evolution, cognitive science,
459 and artificial intelligence (Enquist et al., 2024). Important questions at this intersection include the role of
460 social curiosity in the development of social learning and language acquisition (Oudeyer and Smith, 2016),
461 the role of culture in shaping exploration strategies underlying curiosity-driven learning (Colas et al., 2022a;
462 Moulin-Frier, 2022), and how understanding the cultural evolution of goals might inform the design of AI

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